

Full-Core Modeling and Depletion Benchmarking of the X-10 Graphite Reactor

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ABSTRACT

During the past decade, computational capabilities have evolved significantly for reactor modeling simulation, particularly for Monte Carlo codes. Although continuous-energy Monte Carlo codes remain the gold standard, they remain computationally expensive for full-core depletion calculations. In this work, a full-core model of the historic X-10 Graphite Reactor, a precursor to the Oak Ridge National Laboratory site, was created and simulated using the Shift Monte Carlo code. The reactor was the first continuously operating nuclear reactor in the world, and its fuel slugs were some of the first man-made irradiated nuclear material. Representative loading of the reactor with 43,000 fuel slugs was achieved with full-core depletion with the Exnihilo/Omnibus front end. The simulated isotope results were individually tracked in a burnup calculation for each slug and compared to nondestructive measurements performed by Savannah River National Laboratory, specifically fission product isotope activities of ¹⁵²Eu, ¹⁵⁴Eu, and ¹³⁷Cs from seven fuel slugs. Given uncertainty in the sample and reactor history, the simulation efforts were able to predict isotopics in agreement with Savannah River National Laboratory measurements. The full-core depletion results provide higher resolution data for fission product isotope ratios with respect to reactor position and irradiation length than previously available in the literature. This work displays how full-core depletion simulations can be used to explore wider isotopic distributions for fuel samples originating from a single channel.

Keywords: X-10 Graphite Reactor, full-core depletion, isotopic benchmarking

1. INTRODUCTION

The Graphite Reactor at the X-10 site is one of the oldest nuclear reactor sites in the world. The Graphite Reactor demonstrated the capability of continuous reactor operation, which served as an example for the future commercial nuclear reactors. After the Chicago Pile-1 (CP-1) demonstrated the first man-made nuclear reaction, the Graphite Reactor served an important role demonstrating plutonium production during the Manhattan Project. After production ended, the reactor became an important resource for the earliest studies in radiation damage, radioisotope production, health physics, and element discovery, among others. The original site that housed the Graphite Reactor became what is now Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL).

The Graphite Reactor (or “pile”) achieved its first criticality on November 4, 1943, around 5:00 a.m. The reactor was a graphite-moderated and air-cooled system with inlet and outlet manifolds that provided

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Figure 1. Front face of the X-10 graphite reactor (left) and core loading diagram from postproduction operation with zone numbers labeled (right)

air flow during operations at negative relative pressure. The reactor held approximately 30,000 fuel slugs at initial criticality. This achievement marked a significant milestone in the Manhattan Project because it enabled the initial production of plutonium in a continuously operating fashion. The reactor produced plutonium from its initial criticality until several production reactors at the Hanford Site came online in 1944–1945 [1]. The design and operation of X-10 helped inform the successor Hanford reactors, although the latter required water as a moderator to allow for sufficient cooling. A history of the X-10 reactor is not intended here as many other resources provide detailed information on its history and its initial criticality [2].

The slugs irradiated in the graphite pile are some of the oldest anthropogenic irradiated material in the world. Such samples are difficult to procure and provide unique opportunities for benchmarking. Few models of the X-10 Graphite Reactor have been created, and higher-fidelity models can more accurately address the neutron physics [3]. Current computational methods and architecture provide the capability to do so at high fidelity, even within Monte Carlo codes where high-fidelity depletion calculations are computationally expensive [4, 5]. Benchmarking with high-fidelity models can help provide references for spent fuel characterization studies of graphite-moderated reactors [6].

The goal of this paper is threefold. The first goal is to create a full-core model of the X-10 Graphite Reactor. The second goal is to perform full-core depletion calculations with the model to calculate accurate isotope concentrations in all fuel slugs for spent fuel characterization. The third goal is to compare the results of the model to literature results from experimentally measured samples.

2. X-10 GRAPHITE REACTOR DESIGN AND SAMPLE INFORMATION

The X-10 graphite pile was a graphite-moderated, air-cooled thermal reactor. The pile is nearly a cube with 24 ft (≈ 7.3 m) to a side. The fuel was natural uranium slugs, which originally were sheathed in aluminum cladding (“jackets”) but later were annealed with an Al-Si eutectic to improve safety and performance [7]. The slugs were loaded horizontally into fuel channels where they could fall out the back face of the reactor into a cooling pond. The reactor consisted of 1,248 fuel channels from the front face of the reactor, although the reactor often operated with two-thirds of the channels containing fuel. Each fuel channel could hold up to 65 fuel slugs, although the average loading was near 50 slugs. The pile contained a series of regulating, shim, and safety rods for reactivity control inserted from the top and sides [8].

Table I. X-10 Graphite Reactor parameters and sample information

X-10 Graphite Reactor parameters [10]	Pile	
	Nominal power (MW)	3.5
	Total fuel channels	1,248
	Number of active channels	821
	Number of slugs	41,000
	Average flux (n/cm ² /s)	5×10^{11}
	Slug pitch (cm)	20.32
	Fuel slugs	
	Material	Natural uranium
	U mass (kg)	1.17
Length (cm)	10.80	
Diameter (cm)	3.02	
Clad thickness (cm)	0.089	
Irradiated fuel slug parameters	SRNL sample Information [11]	
	Row-column pair	1479
	Days in pile (assumes irradiation)	1,822
	Percent of max flux	52%
	Accumulated exposure (kWh)	1.45×10^8
	NVT [†]	5.35×10^{19}
	Derived values from SRNL information	
	Flux (n/cm ² /s)	5.72×10^{11}
Average power (MW)	3.32	
Reactor uptime	94.8%	
Total time in pile (d)	1,922	

[†]NVT is not explicitly defined in Ref. [11] but is an old term for neutron fluence and is assumed to be units n/cm² based on multiplication of the flux and irradiation time

Table I lists some of the relevant operational parameters of the reactor. Although some of the operational characteristics and history are known, much of it was unavailable or untracked at the time. Lack of precise historical data accompanies many modeling efforts of old reactors, as was the case with CP-1 and recent efforts with unknown material and geometry information [9]. For example, the reactor went critical at 1.0 MW, peaked at 4.0 MW, and operated postproduction at a nominal power of 3.5 MW. However, sources indicate the reactor operated during its postproduction days from around 3.3 to 4.0 MW [10]. Additionally, the exact reactor up-time remains unknown; however, one source indicates a routine shutdown for about a half-day notionally every week for maintenance [7]. Assuming this consistent shutdown for this period of time, its capacity factor was 93%. The slugs are assumed to not be individually tracked, and it is not known which slugs were in the reactor and for what duration(s).

A report by Aucott from Savannah River National Laboratory (SRNL) details a series of nondestructive assay measurements on seven full-length slugs discharged from the reactor following 5 years of irradiation from 1945 to 1950 [11]. SRNL measurements included the activities of ²³⁸U, ¹⁵²Eu, ¹⁵⁴Eu, and ¹³⁷Cs with a high-purity germanium detector. The list of parameters relevant for the SRNL samples is also shown in Table I. The sample was in the radial midregion of the core (i.e., not at the center of the core nor the periphery).

3. MODELING TOOLS AND METHODOLOGY

This work creates a benchmark model for a high-fidelity core model and compares to spent fuel measurements. X-10 provides a unique benchmarking opportunity as much of its design information has

Figure 2. X-10 Graphite Reactor models visualized with the SCALE Fulcrum tool [15]

been made public, and it was used in post-production days for the earliest reactor studies on radioisotope production, materials irradiation, and element discovery. For this paper, the Shift Monte Carlo code [12] was used as part of the Exnihilo code suite with the Omnibus front end [13]. The Shift Monte Carlo code is a powerful computational tool built for massively parallel calculations, and the nuclide depletion capabilities were vastly improved with a multilevel parallelization scheme [14]. Some initial geometry models were created and run with the Shift code as part of the SCALE software package [15]. However, all of the models were run with the Exnihilo/Omnibus front end, which can use SCALE inputs for geometry generation and user-defined tallies and depletion parameters.

Examples of models visualized with the SCALE Fulcrum tool are shown in Figure 2. Pin-cell, full channel, and full-core models were created for models of increasing complexity. The full-core model consists of the 35×36 fuel channel blocks in graphite. No reactivity control mechanisms were added in the model due to uncertainty in their position and movement with irradiation.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Neutronics Results

The full-core model was run with the Shift Monte Carlo Code as part of the Exnihilo code suite. The ENDF-B/VII.1 nuclear data library was used with continuous energy capability within Shift. The simulation used 10^7 particles per cycle with 100 skipped and 500 total cycles. The depletion calculation utilized 60 cores each with 20 GB of memory and completed in about 5400 CPU-hours (4 days of wall time) on an ORNL computational cluster. The depletion calculation consisted of 30 time steps. The HDF5 output typically returned with Shift totaled 19 GB. The k_{eff} varied within the range of [1.001,1.006] with less than 3 pcm statistical error for all time steps.

One of the goals was to examine whether the full-core could be depleted with unique materials for each slug. The model contains approximately 43,000 fuel slugs according to the loading diagram in Figure 1. The full-core models were run with constant power depletion steps at the nominal power of 3.5 MW for a total of 10 years of irradiation. This length of time is deemed sufficient because it is double the

length of irradiation of the samples. The first five time steps were 1, 4, 25, 30, and 40 (total of 100 days) followed by a series of 100-day time steps and finally several 200-day time steps.

The flux was obtained in all regions for all time steps because this is the default output in Shift for depletion zones. Figure 3 shows the flux spectrum and profile in the sample channel. Despite the evidently different magnitudes, this range of fluxes suggests the possible flux and spectrum experienced by the sample during irradiation. The spectrum is consistent among fuel channels in the reactor with 54%/32%/14% falling in the thermal/intermediate/fast ranges (thermal <0.5 eV, fast >0.1 MeV).

Figure 3. Neutron flux spectrum for the center and edge of the channel of the sample (left). Flux magnitude along the length of the channel (right).

4.2. Isotope Benchmarking Results

Here, the depletion calculation results for all the slugs are compared to results from the SRNL slugs. Depletion of 40,000 unique-material slugs was achieved for 30 time steps up to 10 years of irradiation. The SRNL slugs originated from a particular channel (1479) in the bottom-left quadrant of the reactor. Despite this knowledge, this study considers the isotope concentrations for all channels as they are generated from the full-core depletion calculations. The reason for comparison to full-core data is due to a combination of factors, including 1) the uncertainty of the position within the channel, 2) general uncertainty related to core operating parameters as they relate to modeling efforts [9], and 3) the availability of the full-core data as provided a successful Shift depletion calculation. For all isotopes considered, they are decayed from the end of irradiation to approximate SRNL measurement dates (1950–2019 or 69 years).

SNRL measured the slugs for several fission product activities, ^{137}Cs , ^{152}Eu , and ^{154}Eu plus ^{238}U . Cesium-137 ($t_{1/2} = 30$ y) is a major fission product that is linearly correlated to burnup [16]. Europium-152 ($t_{1/2} = 13.5$ y) and europium-154 ($t_{1/2} = 8.6$ y) are both fission products that are generally produced from neutron capture on the stable Eu isotopes: ^{151}Eu ($\sigma_{n,g} = 9184$ b) and ^{153}Eu ($\sigma_{n,g} = 312$ b), respectively, for thermal neutrons. Because their production requires two successive neutron reactions, they have a quadratic relationship with respect to neutron fluence (or, closely, burnup). The results also include activities for ^{238}U , which is advantageous because it allows for normalization. The simulations tracked the isotope concentrations of each slug individually, therefore 43,000 isotope concentrations exist for each time step.

The graphs from the SRNL report [11], including derived values from the activities of the four isotopes, were recreated with the simulation data and are shown in Figure 4. Two distinctions can be made between the plots for this work as compared to SRNL. First, the results here are normalized to the ^{238}U

activity because the range in the SRNL-measured ^{238}U activities was around 10%. Second, the ^{137}Cs activity is normalized to the ^{238}U activity for similar reasons as the ^{137}Cs is a known burnup monitor and burnup is typically normalized to heavy metal content (in this case mostly ^{238}U).

Interestingly, the SRNL report shows singular quadratic curves for both ^{152}Eu (Figure 4a) and ^{154}Eu (Figure 4c), evidently because the slugs originated from the same channel and therefore experience similar neutron flux magnitudes. However, when taking into account the ^{137}Cs to ^{238}U normalization, the two curves have a wider spread when examining the full-core simulation data. The ^{154}Eu data is wider spread due to the 1.5 order of magnitude difference in the parents' capture cross sections. The spread is not wide enough for the ^{152}Eu , and nearly all of the simulation points fall on same quadratic curve independent of core location. Nonetheless, the ^{152}Eu (Figure 4a) shows higher sensitivity to irradiation length as illustrated by the breadth of the curves.

Figure 4 also shows the time-isolated full-core curves commensurate with the listed irradiation times of the samples. In other words, Figure 4b and Figure 4d show how well the 3D core model can predict sample isotopics given core power and layout and are placed besides the same plot including all time steps to understand this particular time relative to all irradiation times. Again, ^{154}Eu shows nearly no sensitivity as the curve overlaps with irradiation times that differ by a factor of two. A more quantitative comparison requires future work.

The final two parts, Figure 4e and Figure 4f, show the ratio of the $^{152}\text{Eu}/^{154}\text{Eu}$ in an activity ratio vs the same relative $^{137}\text{Cs}/^{238}\text{U}$ activity ratio. The SRNL report shows that the experimental data relative to a constant line (i.e., the $^{152}\text{Eu}/^{154}\text{Eu}$ ratio is more independent of the ^{137}Cs ratio). This assumption makes sense when the two europium ratios are indeed both quadratic as a function of burnup. The full-core results show that this is indeed not the case because of the varying quadratic slopes of Figure 4a, although distinct contours are still shown for each irradiation time. Figure 4f shows overlapping points for several of the experimental points lined up with the proper irradiation time for the sample.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The goal of this work was to create and simulate a full-core, 3D depletion model of the X-10 Graphite Reactor and compare to experimental measurements for benchmarking some of the oldest and most unique irradiated samples in the world. The model was created and successfully run with the Shift Monte Carlo code with the Exnihilo front end, which shows good performance for full-core depletion calculations that are typically computationally expensive for Monte Carlo codes. The full-core results are compared to isotopic measurements from SRNL. This comparison overall shows good agreement, particularly in matching the sample isotopics given the known irradiation time. This work furthered the understanding of the distribution of europium and cesium activities in the samples relative to the full core. Although the relative ^{154}Eu activity provides low sensitivity to irradiation time, ^{152}Eu shows higher sensitivity due to the larger capture cross section of ^{151}Eu relative to ^{153}Eu . In this specific case, the ^{152}Eu relative amount could aid in interpretation of samples with unknown irradiation time. This work provided more interpretation of isotope concentration results for the full core, which could not be done solely with a handful of samples.

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(a) ^{152}Eu relative to ^{238}U for all slugs in the full-core model for all depletion steps (b) ^{152}Eu relative to ^{238}U for all slugs in the full-core model for irradiation time of 5 years

(c) ^{154}Eu relative to ^{238}U for all slugs in the full-core model all depletion steps (d) ^{154}Eu relative to ^{238}U for all slugs in the full-core model for irradiation time of 5 years

(e) $^{154}\text{Eu}/^{152}\text{Eu}$ activity ratio relative to ^{238}U for all slugs in the full-core model for all depletion steps (f) $^{154}\text{Eu}/^{152}\text{Eu}$ activity ratio relative to ^{238}U for all slugs in the full-core model for irradiation time of 5 years

Figure 4. Isotope activities and activity ratios for the full core model of 40,000 slugs compared to experimental data from SRNL slugs [11]. The left panels show the results for each slug in the reactor for all model time steps. The right panels show truncation of the data to only include the 5 years irradiation time of the samples.

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